

Track 2 Lightning Talk: Should CITATION files be standardized?

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1 Introduction

CITATION files [Wilson, 2013] are a central strategy for directing, and rendering possible, attribution and credit for research software, as outlined, e.g., in Smith et al. [2016]. Similar to LICENSE files, they rely on their discovery and due application. Unlike software licenses, however, which are legally binding and actionable, the intended use of reference information in a CITATION file depends on the application of Good Scientific Practice by, e.g., the researcher who uses a software to produce a paper. In this context, it is essential that the information in a CITATION file is highly visible for users of a software.

A brief survey of citation files on GitHub (<https://github.com/search?q=filename%3Acitation&type=Code&utf8=%E2%9C%93>) reveals great variety in syntax, format, contents, names and extensions of CITATION files. Some files, most prominently R [R Development Core Team, 2008] package citation files, use a syntax, while most are simply free form plain or marked-up text, partly containing BibTEX entries for re-use in TEX bibliographies.

It seems that in order to create greater visibility for files containing reference information, they should follow a defined syntax and be machine-readable. Machine-readability would allow for their re-use in a number of contexts:

- They can be read at runtime, and their contents formatted and provided to users in the GUI, or in log messages, of the research software itself.
- Software repositories can re-use them to prominently provide citation information to users similar to, e.g., the way GitHub displays license information.¹
- They can be used as a source for a collection of metadata for a software, e.g., a CodeMeta [Jones et al., 2017] JSON-LD file.
- They can be used as a source for collecting transitive credit information [Katz and Smith, 2015] for a product.
- They can be used as a source for creating citation files for other systems, such as the R package citation system.

¹Depending on where a CITATION file is located in the directory tree, reference information could thus be provided granularly, for different levels of the software, e.g., files or packages implementing a citable algorithm, applications and libraries, or containers bundling several applications and libraries.

While the machine-readability of CITATION files is essential to provide possibilities for greater visibility of reference information for research software, they should still remain as human-readable as possible, as they will often be packaged with shipped products and are thus targeted at end-users of differing technical skill sets. This constraint could be fulfilled by using, for example, a RIS-based [Thomson-Reuters, 2009] format, extended with an optional tag for messages as often found in CITATION files (“If you use this software in your work, please cite ...”), or even a tag for a plain-text version of the citation file contents. RIS also has the advantage of providing a reference type COMP, i.e., computer program, in contrast to the less strictly typed B_BT_EX format.

In addition to the proposed format, files containing reference information should also be consistently named, e.g., CITATION (in analogy to LICENSE and NOTICE files).

In order to promote a unified name and format for CITATION files, communities such as the WSSSPE or RSE community could collaborate in providing tooling for creators of and contributors to research software, in order to smooth the way for wide adoption of standardized CITATION files. Such tooling could consist of a web service or platform for the creation of CITATION files as well as software libraries for reading their contents in different programming languages.

All in all, standardized CITATION files as described above represent a compromise between the commonly used free form citation files as found in code repositories, and a more elaborate transitive credit system implemented in JSON-LD, which is given as an alternative to CITATION files by Smith et al. [2016].

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